

Review Article

Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*): Multi-Target Phytotherapeutic Agent with Pharmacological Evidence and Future Nano-Phytomedicine Approaches

Mahesh Saralaya*, Manali Thorat

Annasaheb Dange College of B Pharmacy, Ashta, Sangli, Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi/Giloy), a cornerstone of Ayurvedic medicine, is renowned for its immunomodulatory, adaptogenic, and rejuvenating properties. Its rich phytochemical profile including alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides, flavonoids, polysaccharides, and steroids underpins a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, cardioprotective, and antimicrobial effects. Mechanistic studies highlight modulation of inflammatory signaling, enhancement of endogenous antioxidant defenses, and protection against cellular and oxidative damage. Emerging research in nano-phytomedicine, gut-brain axis modulation, and network pharmacology indicates enhanced bioavailability and multi-target therapeutic potential. Despite robust preclinical evidence, clinical translation remains limited, underscoring the need for standardized extracts and well-designed human trials. *T. cordifolia* exemplifies a natural therapeutic that integrates traditional wisdom with modern scientific innovation.

INTRODUCTION

The Unani and Ayurvedic systems of medicine, rooted in holistic approaches to health, have long utilized natural resources, particularly medicinal plants, for therapeutic purposes.^[1] Among these, *Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers, commonly known as Guduchi or Giloy, occupies a prominent position due to its broad pharmacological and ethnomedical uses.^[2] In India, China, and other

Asian nations, various plant parts such as the stem, leaves, and roots have long been utilised in traditional medicine as well as in formal systems like Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha.^[3]

In Ayurvedic medicine, *Tinospora cordifolia* is classified as a Rasayana, a category of drugs known for promoting longevity, enhancing immunity, and improving overall health and vitality.^[4] Historically, Guduchi has been

***Corresponding Author:** Mahesh Saralaya

Address: Annasaheb Dange College of B Pharmacy, Ashta, Sangli, Maharashtra, India

Email ✉: mahesh.saralayaadcbp@gmail.com

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prescribed for the management of chronic fevers, metabolic disorders, liver diseases, inflammatory conditions, and immune dysfunctions.^[5] Its bitter taste (Tikta rasa), rejuvenating nature, and ability to restore physiological balance have contributed to its widespread traditional use in disorders such as diabetes mellitus, arthritis, jaundice, and recurrent infections.^[6]

Tinospora cordifolia's rich phytochemical composition, which contains alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides, steroids, polysaccharides, and flavonoids, is largely responsible for its therapeutic significance.^[7] These phytoconstituents exhibit significant biological activity and are responsible for the plant's antioxidant, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects.^[8] Due to its broad therapeutic spectrum and long-standing traditional use, Guduchi has attracted increasing scientific interest as a potential source of novel bioactive compounds for modern drug development.^[9]

The plant has different local names in India:^[10-15]

- **Latin name:** *Tinospora cordifolia*
- **English name:** Guduchi, Giloy
- **Hindi name:** Giloy, Amrita
- **Tamil name:** Seenthil kodi
- **Malayalam name:** Amruthavalli
- **Marathi name:** Gulvel
- **Telugu name:** Amruthakodi
- **Kannada name:** Amruthavalli
- **Bengali name:** Giloy
- **Oriya name:** Amrutapana

Tinospora cordifolia (family Menispermaceae) is referred to by different names in different places. In India, it is commonly called "Giloy" or "Guduchi," while in Myanmar it is known as "Hnget-htet".^[16] The genus *Tinospora* includes

about 34 species, which are widely distributed in tropical regions of India, Sri Lanka, and Southeast Asia.^[17] In traditional Ayurvedic medicine, for generations, *Tinospora cordifolia* has been used to treat a wide range of illnesses, including fever, diabetes, jaundice, urinary problems, and immune system issues.^[18,19]

The medicinal importance of *T. cordifolia* is attributed to the the presence of several phytochemicals, including as alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides, steroids, polysaccharides, and flavonoids.^[20-22] These phytochemicals are bioactive substances that play a protective role in plants and exert significant pharmacological effects in humans, making them valuable for the development of therapeutic agents.^[23] Each plant species may contain different active compounds, thereby offering a wide range of health benefits.^[24]

Additionally, *Tinospora cordifolia* is considered rejuvenating (Rasayana), immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, and antipyretic.^[25,26] It is widely used for enhancing immunity, managing chronic fevers, controlling blood sugar levels, and improving general health.^[27,28]

Scientific Classification

- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Clade:** Tracheophytes
- **Clade:** Angiosperms
- **Order:** Ranunculales
- **Family:** Menispermaceae
- **Genus:** *Tinospora*
- **Species:** *T. cordifolia* ^[29-32]

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive literature survey was carried out using various scientific databases, including Google Scholar, Science-Direct, PubMed,

Publons, and ResearchGate. Relevant literature was identified using keywords such as *Tinospora cordifolia*, phytochemicals, pharmacological activities, traditional uses, and Ayurvedic significance. Peer-reviewed research articles, review papers, pharmacopoeial monographs, and classical Ayurvedic texts were included to ensure the authenticity and reliability of the collected information.^[33–35]

AYURVEDIC SIGNIFICANCE

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi/Amrita) has been widely utilised for ages in traditional Ayurvedic medicine, and practically every element of the plant has a major positive impact on human health. The plant has been incorporated into various Ayurvedic and folk medicinal preparations, including juices, decoctions, pastes, powders, and pills, for the management of general debility, chronic fever, skin diseases, persistent diarrhea, jaundice, asthma, bone fractures, and metabolic disorders. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe Guduchi under several therapeutic categories such as Rasayana, Sangrahi, Balya, Agnideepana, Tridoshaghna, Dahaprashamana, Mehahara, Kasa-Swasahara, Pandunashaka, Kamala-Kushta-Vatarakta-Nashaka, Jwarahara, Krimihara, Prameha, Arshahara, and Hridroga-Nashaka.^[36–41]

Amrita is traditionally regarded as a blood purifier and is believed to eliminate impaired and red blood cells that are destroyed from peripheral circulation. Owing to its high alkaloidal content and well-documented therapeutic potential, the stem of *Tinospora cordifolia* has been officially recognized as a medicinal drug in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India.^[36]

The leaves of the plant are used in powdered form or as a decoction, often administered along with cow's milk, for the treatment of gout, ulcers, jaundice, fever, wounds, and for the regulation of

blood glucose levels.^[37–39] In certain regions of North Gujarat (India), the bark, roots, and stem are traditionally employed for the treatment of various diseases. The stem extract is commonly used as a therapeutic formulation for jaundice, fever, dermatological disorders, and general weakness, while stem starch (Guduchi Satva) is widely utilized as a rejuvenating tonic. Additionally, a combination of root and stem is recommended as a remedy for scorpion sting and wind-related disorders. The roots are also traditionally prescribed as an emetic and are used in the management of visceral obstructions, leprosy, diarrhea, and dysentery.^[38–42]

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

According to the Indian Pharmacopoeia standards, a detailed physicochemical evaluation of the stem of *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi) was carried out by various researchers. The analysed parameters included foreign matter, total ash, acid-insoluble ash, water-soluble ash, loss on drying, and extractive values, all of which were within acceptable limits for crude herbal drugs^[43,44]. A comparative investigation of the leaf, stem, and aerial root of Guduchi was also performed. The study revealed measurable variations in ash values, extractive values, and other physicochemical parameters in powdered, air-dried samples, confirming the quality and purity of the plant material.^[45,46]

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content of Guduchi stem extracts made with several solvents, including methanol, hexane, chloroform, and ethyl acetate, was quantitatively evaluated. A modified Folin–Ciocalteu method was employed, with tannic acid as the standard reference. A UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to detect the absorbance at 765 nm. Results demonstrated that

the ethyl acetate extract had the highest phenolic content (9.8 µg/g), followed by methanol, chloroform, and hexane extracts. The hexane extract exhibited the lowest phenolic content (4.8 µg/g), indicating solvent-dependent extraction efficiency of phenolic compounds from the Guduchi stem. [47,48]

Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content of Guduchi stem extracts made using methanol, hexane, chloroform, and ethyl acetate was determined using the aluminium chloride colorimetric method, with quercetin as the standard reference. A UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to detect absorbance at 415 nm. The methanolic extract of Guduchi stem showed the highest flavonoid content (11.08 µg/g), whereas the hexane extract had the lowest (3.62 µg/g). These results indicate that polar solvents such as methanol are more efficient in extracting flavonoid compounds from *Tinospora cordifolia* stem. [49,50]

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) is an abundant source of many bioactive phytochemicals, which are principally in charge of its extensive pharmacological actions. The major classes of chemical constituents include alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides, steroids, polysaccharides, and flavonoids. [51-56]

Alkaloids

The plant contains alkaloids such as tinosporine, berberine, and magnoflorine, which support its anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and antidiabetic properties. [51,52]

Diterpenoid Lactones

Diterpenoid lactones, including tinosporide, cordifolide, and cordioside, exhibit hepatoprotective, anticancer, and antioxidant activities, and are key contributors to the therapeutic efficacy of the plant. [52,53]

Flavonoids

Quercetin, kaempferol, and isorhamnetin are examples of flavonoids that have cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. These substances prevent oxidative damage to cells by acting as free radical scavengers. [53,54]

Glycosides

Key glycosides, including cordioside and tinocordiside, demonstrate anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties, enhancing the overall therapeutic potential of *T. cordifolia*. [54,55]

Polysaccharides

Polysaccharides, such as arabinogalactans and glucans, play a key role in immunostimulatory, antioxidant, and antitumor activities. They also act as natural stabilizers in nanoparticle synthesis in green nanotechnology applications. [55,56]

Steroids

Plant steroids like β-sitosterol and stigmasterol exhibit anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic, and cholesterol-lowering activities, making them valuable for metabolic and cardiovascular health. [56]

Other Compounds

Additional constituents such as alkylresorcinols and sesquiterpenes show antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, and antidiabetic effects, supporting the multifunctional therapeutic properties of the plant. Collectively, the complex

phytochemical profile of *Tinospora cordifolia* validated through both traditional use and modern underlies its pleiotropic pharmacological actions, experimental studies. [56]

Figure 1. Chemical structures of major phytoconstituents isolated from *Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers.

(1) Tinosporaside; (2) Cordifolioside A; (3) Columbin; (4) Magnoflorine; (5) Berberine; (6) Syringin.

Figure 2: *Tinospora Cordifolia*

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION

Willd. *Tinospora cordifolia* Miers is a huge, perennial, deciduous climbing shrub with long, twining branches that frequently grows over trees and other supports. It is a member of the Menispermaceae family. [57] The stem is cylindrical, succulent, glabrous, greenish to light grey, and has noticeable lenticels that taste very

bitter. Aerial roots emerge from the nodes of mature stems, appearing long, thread-like, and brownish-grey, aiding the plant in its climbing habit. [58]

The leaves are simple, alternate, and cordate, measuring about 6–15 cm in length, with long petioles and a membranous, smooth, glabrous lamina. Reticulate venation is clearly visible on

both surfaces, with the upper surface dark green and the lower surface lighter in color. [59]

Tinospora cordifolia is dioecious, producing small, greenish-yellow, unisexual flowers arranged in axillary or terminal racemose inflorescences. Male flowers occur in clusters, whereas typically, female blooms are solitary. Typically, flowers bloom from March to June. [60]

The fruit is an ovoid to globose drupe, approximately 8–12 mm in diameter, turning bright red upon ripening and containing a single curved seed. A characteristic anatomical feature of *T. cordifolia* is the radial arrangement of vascular bundles in the stem, an important diagnostic trait. [61]

Figure 1. Whole plant (Habit)

Figure 2. Stem morphology

Figure 3. Aerial roots

Figure 4. Inflorescence

Figure 5. Immature fruits

Figure 8. Mature fruits

Figure 3: Botanical Description of *Tinospora Cordifolia* .

DESCRIPTION AND ETHNOBOTANICAL USES OF *TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA*

Vernacular Names and Ethnomedicinal Usage

Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Miers, is also referred as Guduchi or Giloy, is one of the most revered medicinal plants in traditional systems of medicine. [62] In Sanskrit, it is referred to as Guduchi, Amrita, and Chakralakshanika; in Hindi, Giloy or Gulancha; in Marathi, Gulvel; in Tamil, Seenthil kodi; in Telugu, Tippa teega; in Kannada,

Amruthaballi; in Urdu, Gilo; and in Arabic, Gulanch. [63,64]

T. cordifolia is categorised as a Rasayana in Ayurveda. drug and is extensively used for enhancing immunity, longevity, and vitality. It is traditionally prescribed for the management of fever, diabetes (Prameha), jaundice, urinary disorders, gout, arthritis, and inflammatory conditions. The stem is particularly valued for Its hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, immunomodulatory, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities. [65,66]

In Unani medicine, *T. cordifolia* is employed as a blood purifier and tonic, while in Siddha and folk medicine, it's employed to treat chronic fever, skin disorders, respiratory conditions and overall weakness. [67,68]

In recent years, the plant has gained global attention for its adaptogenic and neuroprotective potential, aligning with modern pharmacological findings supporting its role in neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease. [69,70]

Geographical Distribution and Habitat

Tinospora cordifolia is widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of the Indian subcontinent, covering portions of China and Southeast Asia, Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, and Myanmar. [71] In India, it is commonly found growing wild in deciduous and dry forests, hedges, and wastelands, particularly in warmer regions [72]

The plant is a large, perennial, deciduous climbing shrub that thrives in diverse soil conditions and is often observed climbing on large trees such as neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and mango (*Mangifera indica*) [73] It prefers well-drained soil and tropical climatic conditions and propagates easily through stem cuttings. Due to its hardy nature and extensive ethnomedicinal importance, *T. cordifolia* is widely cultivated and conserved across India for both traditional and pharmaceutical applications. [74]

III. PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Tinospora cordifolia, commonly referred to as Guduchi or Giloy, has a wide range of pharmacological effects that are backed by some clinical, in vitro, and in vivo data. Alkaloids, diterpenoids, glycosides, steroids, flavonoids, and polysaccharides are among the several

phytoconstituents that are principally responsible for these effects. [75]

Antioxidant Activity

Multiple studies demonstrate that *T. cordifolia* extracts significantly enhance endogenous antioxidant systems and reduce oxidative damage. In diabetic rat models, treatment with *T. cordifolia* extracts normalized antioxidant enzyme levels (SOD, CAT, GPx) and reduced thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS), indicating potent free radical scavenging and protective effects against oxidative tissue damage. [76][77]

Bioactive compounds such as phenolics and flavonoids activate Nrf2 signalling, leading to upregulation of antioxidant defences, which may protect against oxidative stress-related diseases. [78] The mechanisms include scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS), enhancing glutathione (GSH) levels, and modulating Nrf2/ARE pathways.

Significant antioxidant capacity is demonstrated by extracts from the plant's roots, leaves, and stems, among other sections. As an example:

When diabetic rats were given aqueous root extracts, their plasma levels of TBARS, ceruloplasmin, and alpha-tocopherol decreased while their levels of glutathione and vitamin C increased, restoring the antioxidant balance under oxidative stress. [79] High levels of radical scavenging activity were demonstrated by leaf extracts in in vitro models.

With an EC₅₀ of 0.5 mg/mL, ethanol extracts demonstrated potent DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging, outperforming other solvents including methanol and chloroform. [80]

In ferric ion-induced liposome models, the plant showed prevention of lipid peroxidation. ^[81] In order to minimise oxidative damage caused by transition metals such as iron, stem extracts demonstrated significant metal ion chelating activity (67–95%) at low concentrations (10–40 µg/mL).^[82] Strong reducing power and antioxidant capacity were correlated with the total phenolic content of different extracts, which ranged from 8.75 to 52.50 catechol equivalents per gramme (CE/g).^[83]

According to these results, *T. cordifolia* increases the activity of endogenous antioxidant enzymes including SOD and CAT in addition to scavenging free radicals. Protection against oxidative stress-related diseases like diabetes, cancer, and neurological disorders further validates its antioxidant qualities. All of these research point to *Tinospora cordifolia* as a promising natural antioxidant with medicinal potential for treating diseases brought on by oxidative stress.^{[84][85]}

Antidiabetic and Metabolic Effects

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) has been widely reported to exhibit antidiabetic and metabolic regulatory activities. It demonstrates significant antihyperglycemic

effects in experimental diabetes models by enhancing insulin secretion, improving peripheral glucose uptake, and reducing postprandial glycemia.^[86]

Additionally, *T. cordifolia* exhibits hypolipidemic effects, lowering total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL, suggesting potential benefits in metabolic syndrome and related disorders.^[87] The mechanisms include modulation of carbohydrate metabolizing enzymes, improved insulin sensitivity, and reduction of oxidative stress.^[88]

Research has demonstrated that oral *T. cordifolia* extracts (100–200 mg/kg body weight) lower blood glucose levels in diabetic animal models by promoting insulin secretion and blocking important gluconeogenic enzymes including fructose-1,6-diphosphatase and glucose-6-phosphatase. According to histological investigations employing periodic acid–Schiff staining, it also replenishes the amount of glycogen in the liver.^[89]

Through both insulin-dependent and insulin-independent mechanisms, the plant increases peripheral tissues' absorption of glucose. For instance, in skeletal muscle cells, stem extracts increase the activity of the glucose transporters GLUT1 and GLUT3 for basal glucose uptake and GLUT4 for insulin-mediated glucose transport. Increased phosphorylation of two important glucose metabolism regulators, Protein Kinase B (AKT) and AMP-Activated Protein Kinase (AMPK), supports this.^[90]

T. cordifolia protects pancreatic beta cells against inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β and interferon- γ , allowing for natural insulin synthesis.^[91] Oxidative stress, a major contributor to *T. cordifolia*, helps to battle diabetes by increasing antioxidant defences. It boosts antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, GPx, and GSH while decreasing oxidative stress indicators like TBARS.^[92] Tinosporaside is one of several bioactive components that were separated from *Tinospora cordifolia* that have strong pharmacological properties, including immunomodulation, anticancer, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory actions. Clinical research points to insulin-like action that successfully lowers blood sugar levels without causing acute harm or altering behaviour. Tinosporaside has the potential to be a natural medicinal agent for the control of diabetes since it increases insulin sensitivity,

lowers fasting blood glucose levels, and improves lipid profiles by decreasing triglycerides and total cholesterol.^{[93][94]}

Immunomodulatory Activity

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) is one of the most studied immunomodulatory herbs in Ayurveda. Experimental studies have demonstrated macrophage activation, enhanced phagocytosis, increased natural killer (NK) cell activity, and modulation of cytokines such as IL-6 and TNF- α .^[95] Polysaccharides and immunoactive proteins from *T. cordifolia* stimulate both innate and adaptive immunity, contributing to systemic immunomodulatory effects.^[96] The mechanisms include cytokine modulation, enhanced antigen presentation, and immune cell activation.^[97]

Its wide range of bioactive substances, such as alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, polysaccharides, glycosides, and phenolics, are mainly responsible for the immunomodulatory effects. Together, these substances influence immunological responses. *T. cordifolia* extracts, for instance, increase cytokines like IL-6, boosting inflammatory reactions and encouraging B cell and cytotoxic T cell development.^[98] Polysaccharides derived from the plant modulate cytokine release and nitric oxide production in macrophages, offering protection against endotoxic shock.^[99] Aqueous extracts of *T. cordifolia* increase macrophage activity via increasing lysosomal secretion and nitric oxide production, both of which are required for pathogen clearance. Animal studies have shown that the plant boosts antioxidant enzyme levels, lowering oxidative damage in vital organs such as the liver and spleen.^[100] Specific compounds, such as alpha-d-glucan, promote lymphocyte activation while reducing inflammatory mediators, hence enhancing adaptive immunity.^[101]

Clinical studies have shown that individuals, particularly youngsters, produce more antibodies against numerous antigens and have stronger immunological responses.^[102] Syringin and other bioactive ingredients suppress pro-inflammatory pathways like NF- κ B, resulting in anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.

Overall, these findings highlight *Tinospora cordifolia* as a powerful immunomodulator with potential applications in treating infections and chronic inflammatory diseases, while more study is needed to standardise dosages and establish clinical efficacy in humans.^[103]

Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Activity

Tinospora cordifolia (Giloy) exhibits significant anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects, which are well-supported by preclinical and experimental studies. The herb reduces pro-inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, and inhibits cyclooxygenase (COX) pathways, contributing to its anti-inflammatory action.^[104] Its analgesic activity has been demonstrated in various experimental pain models, validating its traditional use in managing inflammatory and arthritic conditions.^[105] The routes of action include inhibiting NF- κ B, reducing PGE2 synthesis, and downregulating cytokines. In vitro studies using RAW 264.7 macrophage cells demonstrated that the chloroform extract of *T. cordifolia* significantly reduced COX-2 expression and lowered nitric oxide (NO) generation when cells were stimulated with lipopolysaccharides (LPS).^[106] Furthermore, the extract suppressed p38 MAPK phosphorylation and retained NF- κ B in the cytoplasm, resulting in anti-inflammatory effects.

T. cordifolia's antipyretic efficacy has been verified in animal models. The administration of extracts in brewer's yeast-induced pyrexia in mice

resulted in a considerable drop in body temperature, demonstrating their efficacy in fever management.^[107] The phytochemical content, including tinosporaside, stigmasterol, and β -sitosterol, contributes to the medicinal effects. Furthermore, *T. cordifolia* extracts have been demonstrated to improve wound healing by lowering local inflammation and speeding up tissue repair.^[108]

Collectively, these findings highlight *Tinospora cordifolia* as a viable natural therapy for inflammatory diseases and fever, bolstering its widespread traditional medical use.

Hepatoprotective Activity

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) Shows strong hepatoprotective effects in experimental and preclinical studies. Its extracts protect against chemically induced liver toxicity (e.g., paracetamol, CCl₄) by lowering ALT, AST, ALP, and bilirubin and inhibiting lipid peroxidation.^[109] These effects are associated with enhanced antioxidant enzyme activity, stabilization of hepatocellular membranes, and reduced oxidative stress.^[110] The activity is attributed to its rich phytochemicals—alkaloids (berberine, palmatine, jatrorrhizine), diterpenoids, glycosides, and polyphenols—that collectively reduce oxidative stress and inflammation while promoting hepatic cell regeneration. In CCl₄-induced hepatotoxic rats, *T. cordifolia* extract markedly decreases SGOT, SGPT, ALP, and bilirubin, indicating restoration of liver function and prevention of cellular damage.^[111] Furthermore, antioxidant defences are strengthened by overexpression of SOD, CAT, GPx, and GSH, which neutralise reactive oxygen species (ROS) and prevent lipid peroxidation.^[112] Berberine inhibits TNF- α -mediated pro-inflammatory cascades and suppresses iNOS, lowering nitrosative stress and preventing hepatocyte necrosis. Other ingredients,

notably columbin and magnoflorine, enhance liver regeneration by activating PPAR α and modulating dopamine receptor function. *T. cordifolia* has also been demonstrated to protect against hepatotoxicity caused by heavy metals (arsenic, cadmium) and drugs (paracetamol, thioacetamide).^[113]

The plant's capacity to reduce lipid peroxidation, normalise malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, and maintain antioxidant equilibrium highlights its medicinal promise as a natural hepatoprotectant. It is also commonly used in polyherbal formulations to treat jaundice and other liver problems.

Anticancer and Cytotoxic Activity

Emerging studies indicate that *Tinospora cordifolia* (Giloy) possesses potential anticancer properties. Preclinical research reports that its extracts inhibit tumor cell proliferation and induce apoptosis in cancer cells, effects linked to several bioactive constituents, including alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and diterpenoid lactones.^[114]

The mechanisms of anticancer action include regulation of essential cell survival pathways, suppression of angiogenesis, and cell cycle arrest at the G0/G1 or G2/M stages.^[115] Aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *T. cordifolia*, for example, have been shown to exhibit antiproliferative action in cancer models including hepatocellular carcinoma, glioma, breast cancer, prostate cancer, colon cancer, and leukaemia. These extracts lower cyclin D1 expression, increase pro-apoptotic markers (e.g., Bax, caspases), and inhibit anti-apoptotic proteins such as Bcl-2.^[116]

T. cordifolia also modulates signaling pathways associated with tumor growth and metastasis, including NF- κ B, PI3K/Akt, and MAPK pathways. The plant has been demonstrated to

suppress the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). by downregulating markers such as NCAM, MMP-2, and MMP-9, which are critical for cancer invasion and metastasis. [117] Active constituents such as berberine, tinosporaside, and magnoflorine target multiple oncogenic pathways, resulting in reduced proliferation and enhanced apoptosis in cancer cells.

Furthermore, studies suggest a synergistic effect when multiple phytochemicals from *T. cordifolia* are combined, enhancing its overall anticancer efficacy. [118] Although preclinical evidence is promising, Additional well-designed clinical trials are needed to validate these findings, develop standardised doses, and test the safety and efficacy of cancer treatment in humans.

Antimicrobial and Antiviral Activities

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi/Giloy) has broad-spectrum antibacterial properties. Ethanol, chloroform, and methanolic extracts have been shown to suppress a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms, including multidrug-resistant bacterial strains, fungi, and viruses. These activities are mostly due to the presence of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, glycosides, saponins, and tannins. [119]

For example, ethanolic extracts of *T. cordifolia* have demonstrated substantial antibacterial activity against oral pathogens such as *Streptococcus mutans*, with a zone of inhibition of 25.6 mm at a dose of 3 mg, surpassing other herbal extracts. [120] Methanolic extracts have also shown considerable antibacterial action against opportunistic pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, indicating potential usefulness against multidrug-resistant diseases.

T. cordifolia's antifungal action is demonstrated by its ability to inhibit *Candida albicans* with efficacy comparable to mainstream antifungal medications like nystatin. [121] Furthermore, the plant has antiviral properties, with studies indicating reduction of viral replication, possibly through interference with viral protein synthesis and disruption of viral envelopes. [122]

The mechanisms behind its antimicrobial and antiviral actions include disruption of microbial cell membranes, inhibition of biofilm formation, interference with essential metabolic pathways, and enhancement of host immune responses. For example, animal studies have shown that *T. cordifolia* can restore immune function in systemic infections, thereby contributing to pathogen clearance. [123]

Overall, *Tinospora cordifolia* demonstrates significant potential as a natural antimicrobial and antiviral agent, supporting its traditional use and highlighting its relevance in addressing antibiotic resistance and emerging infectious diseases.

Cardioprotective and Antihyperlipidemic Effects

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) has been associated with significant cardioprotective and antihyperlipidemic effects, supported by experimental and pharmacological studies. The plant has been proven to reduce lipid peroxidation, enhance serum lipid profiles, and protect cardiac tissues from oxidative and inflammatory damage, thus minimising the risk of atherosclerosis and myocardial infarction. [124]

In hyperlipidemic animal models, administration of *T. cordifolia* extracts significantly reduces total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and very-low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) levels while increasing high-density lipoprotein

(HDL) levels.^[125] These effects contribute to improved cardiovascular health and prevention of lipid-associated cardiac disorders.

T. cordifolia's cardioprotective efficacy is mostly due to its antioxidant capabilities, which reduce lipid oxidation and endothelial dysfunction. The plant reduces oxidative stress-induced heart damage by increasing endogenous antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx).^[126]

Traditional Ayurvedic texts describe Guduchi as Hridya (heart-friendly) and recommend its use for strengthening cardiac function. Modern pharmacological investigations corroborate these claims, showing that *T. cordifolia* modulates endothelial function, lipid metabolism, and inflammatory pathways, thereby offering comprehensive cardioprotection.^[127]

Overall, the combined antihyperlipidemic, antioxidant, and endothelial protective actions of *Tinospora cordifolia* support its therapeutic potential in the management of cardiovascular diseases and metabolic syndrome.

Anti-stress, Adaptogenic, and Neuroprotective Effects

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi/Giloy) is traditionally described as a potent adaptogen, a claim that is well supported by experimental and clinical studies. Adaptogens are agents that enhance the body's resistance to physical, chemical, and biological stressors while maintaining physiological homeostasis. Preclinical studies have demonstrated that *T. cordifolia* significantly reduces physiological stress markers, improves stress tolerance, and enhances cognitive performance under stress conditions.^[128]

T. cordifolia's anti-stress effect is mediated via modulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which results in reduced stress hormone release and normalisation of stress-related physiological markers.^[129] Clinical trials in people undergoing mental stress have revealed that taking *T. cordifolia* decreases serum glucose, triglyceride, and cholesterol levels while enhancing psychological well-being. These effects were shown to be comparable to traditional anxiolytic drugs like diazepam, but without the sedative side effects.^[130]

In addition to its adaptogenic role, *T. cordifolia* exhibits marked neuroprotective activity. Experimental studies demonstrate that the plant protects neurons against oxidative damage, suppresses neuroinflammatory responses, and enhances endogenous antioxidant defenses in the brain.^[131] These effects are particularly relevant in the context of neurodegenerative disorders, where oxidative stress and inflammation play central roles. The neuroprotective mechanisms include reduction of lipid peroxidation, enhancement of antioxidant enzymes, and modulation of inflammatory mediators in neuronal tissues.^[132]

T. cordifolia also exhibits significant gastroprotective and anti-ulcer activity, which is closely linked to its stress-reducing properties. Experimental ulcer models have shown that the plant significantly reduces ulcer index, protects the gastric mucosa from damage induced by NSAIDs and alcohol, and promotes mucus secretion and mucosal regeneration.^[133] The gastroprotective effect is further supported by inhibition of gastric acid secretion and attenuation of inflammatory damage to the gastric lining.

Overall, the adaptogenic, anti-stress, neuroprotective, and gastroprotective properties of *Tinospora cordifolia* highlight its therapeutic potential in managing stress-related disorders,

cognitive dysfunction, neurodegenerative diseases, and gastrointestinal complications, Increasing its widespread usage in traditional medicine and modern pharmacology.

Additional Reported Activities

Beyond the major pharmacological activities such as antioxidant, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, cardioprotective, antimicrobial, and adaptogenic effects, *Tinospora cordifolia* has been reported to exhibit several additional bioactivities in traditional medicine and experimental studies. These activities further support the broad therapeutic potential of Guduchi and validate its extensive use in Ayurveda.

T. cordifolia has demonstrated antipyretic and analgesic effects in various experimental fever and pain models. Studies using brewer's yeast-induced pyrexia and nociceptive assays such as the hot plate and writhing tests have shown significant reductions in body temperature and pain responses following administration of *T. cordifolia* extracts. These effects are attributed to Inhibition of prostaglandin production and regulation of proinflammatory mediators. [134] The plant also exhibits significant anti-ulcer and gastroprotective activity. Experimental studies have reported that *T. cordifolia* extracts reduce gastric acid secretion, enhance mucus production, and protect the gastric mucosa from damage induced by stress, NSAIDs, and alcohol. These gastroprotective effects are linked to antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms that preserve mucosal integrity. [135]

Emerging evidence suggests that *T. cordifolia* possesses osteoprotective properties. Preclinical studies indicate that its extracts promote osteoblast proliferation, enhance mineralization, and suppress bone resorption, thereby supporting bone metabolism and skeletal health. These effects are

particularly relevant in conditions such as osteoporosis and inflammatory bone disorders and are believed to be mediated through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory pathways. [136]

Traditional texts and experimental observations also describe antiparasitic properties, including anti-leprotic and anti-malarial activities. These effects are thought to arise from both direct antiparasitic action and immunostimulatory mechanisms that enhance host defense responses. Although clinical evidence remains limited, these activities align with the traditional use of Guduchi as a febrifuge and immune-enhancing agent in chronic infectious conditions. [137]

Collectively, these additional pharmacological activities reinforce the concept of *Tinospora cordifolia* as a multi-target therapeutic plant, capable of modulating diverse biological pathways and supporting its classification as a Rasayana herb in Ayurveda.

Antipyretic and Analgesic Effects

Tinospora cordifolia has been traditionally used for the management of fever and pain, and these effects are well supported by experimental pharmacological studies. In animal models, commercially available extracts of Guduchi significantly increased pain threshold in the hot plate test and reduced writhing responses in the acetic acid-induced abdominal writhing test, indicating both central and peripheral analgesic activities. The analgesic and antipyretic actions are primarily mediated through inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis, modulation of nociceptive pathways, and suppression of inflammatory mediators. [138, 139]

Anti-ulcer and Gastroprotective Activity

Several experimental studies have demonstrated that *T. cordifolia* extracts exhibit significant gastroprotective activity by reducing the severity of experimentally induced gastric ulcers in animal models. These protective effects are attributed to enhancement of mucosal defense mechanisms, increased gastric mucus secretion, suppression of gastric acid secretion, and antioxidant activity that protects the gastric mucosa from oxidative and inflammatory damage. Protective efficacy has been observed in pylorus ligation- and stress-induced ulcer models. [140, 141]

Anti-diarrhoeal Activity

Guduchi has shown notable anti-diarrhoeal activity in castor oil- and magnesium sulfate-induced diarrhoea models in albino rats. The extracts significantly reduced intestinal motility and fluid secretion, possibly through modulation of intestinal smooth muscle activity and inhibition of prostaglandin-mediated secretory mechanisms. [142]

Parkinson's Disease

Tinospora cordifolia has demonstrated promising neuroprotective benefits in Parkinson's disease animals. In MPTP-induced parkinsonian mouse models, aqueous extracts exhibited significant anti-inflammatory effects and protected dopaminergic neurons by reversing neuroinflammation. Treatment with the extract also improved behavioral abnormalities associated with MPTP intoxication. These neuroprotective effects are attributed to the plant's diverse bioactive constituents and antioxidant properties. [149]

NOVEL INSIGHTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES ON *TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA*

Despite extensive pharmacological investigations, several promising and underexplored dimensions of *Tinospora cordifolia* remain insufficiently recognized. Beyond its well-documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and neuroprotective properties, emerging scientific paradigms provide new opportunities to reinterpret the therapeutic relevance of this classical Rasayana plant. [154,155]

Nano-Phytochemical Synergy as a Therapeutic Strategy

An emerging and largely unexplored concept involves the synergistic interaction between *Tinospora cordifolia* phytochemicals and nanostructured delivery systems. Green-synthesized nanoparticles derived from *T. cordifolia* extracts may enhance bioavailability and alter pharmacodynamic behaviour by improving cellular uptake, enzyme affinity, and blood-brain barrier permeability. The phytochemical corona formed around these nanoparticles may enable multi-target engagement, particularly relevant for complex neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease. This nano-phytochemical synergy represents a novel translational strategy bridging traditional herbal medicine with modern nanotechnology. [159]

Rasayana Concept Interpreted Through Systems Biology

In Ayurveda, *T. cordifolia* is classified as a Rasayana, traditionally associated with rejuvenation, longevity, and enhancement of cognitive function. From a modern biomedical perspective, these effects may correspond to regulation of oxidative stress, mitochondrial protection, immune-neural homeostasis, and maintenance of proteostasis. Integrating Rasayana theory with systems biology offers a novel

framework to explain the pleiotropic molecular and cellular effects of *T. cordifolia*, which has not yet been systematically explored in contemporary literature.

Potential Role in Gut–Brain Axis Modulation

Recent advances emphasize the role of the gut–brain axis in neurodegenerative and neuroinflammatory disorders. Immunomodulatory polysaccharides present in *T. cordifolia* may act as prebiotic agents, modulating gut microbiota composition and reducing systemic and neuroinflammation. Although direct experimental evidence remains limited, this putative mechanism offers a compelling direction for future research, particularly in Alzheimer’s disease and stress-related neurological disorders. [157,158]

Regulation of Metal Ion Homeostasis in Neurodegeneration

Dysregulated metal ion metabolism involving copper, zinc, and iron contributes to amyloid aggregation and oxidative damage in Alzheimer’s disease. Phytochemicals present in *T. cordifolia*, including alkaloids and phenolic compounds, may possess metal-chelating properties that restore redox balance and inhibit metal-induced neurotoxicity. This hypothesis aligns with growing interest in metal-based nanoparticles and represents an underreported mechanistic pathway for *T. cordifolia*-mediated neuroprotection. [155,159]

Epigenetic Modulation as an Emerging Mechanism

Epigenetic dysregulation plays a critical role in aging and neurodegenerative disorders. Bioactive constituents of *T. cordifolia* may influence epigenetic mechanisms such as DNA methylation, histone modification, and microRNA expression, thereby contributing to sustained anti-

inflammatory and neuroprotective effects. Although experimental validation is required, this emerging concept significantly expands the therapeutic scope of *T. cordifolia* beyond conventional pharmacological mechanisms. [154]

Network Pharmacology and Polypharmacological Potential

Given its complex phytochemical profile, *T. cordifolia* is well-suited for network pharmacology-based investigations. Mapping interactions between its bioactive compounds and multiple molecular targets—including acetylcholinesterase, β -secretase, GSK-3 β , NF- κ B, and Nrf2—could provide a holistic understanding of its multi-target therapeutic actions. Such integrative approaches remain underutilized for *T. cordifolia* and hold significant promise for future drug discovery efforts. [155]

Need for Nano-Standardization and Translational Validation

Despite increasing interest in *T. cordifolia*-based nanomedicine, standardized protocols for nanoformulation, phytochemical fingerprinting, and pharmacokinetic profiling are lacking. Future studies should prioritize nano-standardization markers, bioavailability-guided extraction, and blood–brain barrier permeability assessments to facilitate clinical translation of *Tinospora*-based nano-phytopharmaceuticals. [159]

CONCLUSION

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) is a well-known medicinal herb that has long been used in traditional medicine, particularly Ayurveda. Extensive scientific research over the last few decades has supported many of its traditional claims, revealing a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities including antioxidant,

anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, cardioprotective, antimicrobial, adaptogenic, and anticancer effects. These therapeutic properties are largely attributed to its diverse phytochemical profile, comprising alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides, polysaccharides, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds.

Experimental and preclinical studies have demonstrated that *T. cordifolia* exerts its pharmacological effects through multiple complementary mechanisms such as modulation of inflammatory cytokines, enhancement of endogenous antioxidant defenses, regulation of immune responses, inhibition of key metabolic and neurodegenerative enzymes, and protection against oxidative and cellular damage. Such multi-target actions make Guduchi particularly relevant for the management of complex, multifactorial diseases.

Recent advances in pharmaceutical sciences have further expanded interest in *T. cordifolia*, especially in the context of new medicine delivery techniques and green nanotechnology. Plant-mediated nanoparticle synthesis and network pharmacology approaches offer promising strategies to enhance the bioavailability, stability, and therapeutic efficacy of its bioactive constituents. However, despite encouraging experimental evidence, the clinical translation of *T. cordifolia*-based therapies remains limited due to challenges related to extract standardization, variability in phytochemical composition, and insufficient large-scale clinical studies.

In conclusion, *Tinospora cordifolia* represents a valuable medicinal resource with significant therapeutic potential. Continued interdisciplinary research focusing on standardization, mechanistic validation, safety evaluation, and clinical efficacy is essential to fully integrate this traditional

medicinal plant into evidence-based modern healthcare.

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